

A Revision of Palaearctic *Campiglossa* Species Assigned to *Gonioxyna* (Diptera: Tephritidae)

V. A. Korneyev

Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, UA 252030 Kiev, Ukraine

A Revision of Palaearctic *Campiglossa* Species Assigned to *Gonioxyna* (Diptera: Tephritidae). Korneyev V. A. — The synonymization of *Gonioxyna* and *Campiglossa* is justified. The species formerly placed into *Gonioxyna*, and recently transferred to *Campiglossa*, are redescribed and keyed. All hitherto known materials are revised, and the new data on distribution range is given. *Campiglossa quadriguttata* (Hendel) is the senior synonym of *Campiglossa diribekorum* Norrbom in: Thompson et al., 1997 (as nom. n. pro *dispertita* Dirlbek, Dirlbek, nec *dispertita* Munro), syn. n.

Ревізія видів *Campiglossa*, що відносилися до *Gonioxyna* (Diptera: Tephritidae). Корнеев В. О. — Підтверджено синонімізацію *Gonioxyna* та *Campiglossa*. Переописані види, що раніше були віднесені до *Gonioxyna* і нещодавно переміщені в *Campiglossa*, подано таблицю для їх визначення. Ревізовано всі досі відомі матеріали наведено нові дані з розповсюдження. *Campiglossa quadriguttata* (Hendel) — старший синонім *Campiglossa diribekorum* Norrbom in: Thompson et al., syn. n.

Ревизия видов *Campiglossa*, относившихся к *Gonioxyna* (Diptera: Tephritidae). Корнеев В. О. — Подтверждена синонимизация *Gonioxyna* и *Campiglossa*. Переописаны виды, ранее относившиеся к *Gonioxyna* и недавно перемещенные в *Campiglossa*, дана таблица для их определения. Ревизованы все известные на сегодня материалы, приведены новые данные по распространению. *Campiglossa quadriguttata* (Hendel) — старший синоним *Campiglossa diribekorum* Norrbom in: Thompson et al., syn. n.

This paper continues a series of publications on Palaearctic tephritid flies from the group of genera related to *Paroxyna* Hendel (Korneyev, 1990). In that first paper the genus *Gonioxyna* Hendel was synonymized with *Campiglossa* Rondani, but neither material was listed, nor descriptions were given and discussed.

The type and other specimens are deposited in the following institutions:

Institute of Zoology, Academia Sinica, Beijing (IZAS), Natural History Museum, London (NHML), Naturhistorisches Museum, Wien (NHMW), National Museum, Praha (NMP), Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, Kiev (SIZK), Természettudományi Múzeum Állattára, Budapest (TMB), Zoological Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences, Saint-Petersburg (ZISP), Zoological Museum of Moscow University (ZMUM).

Most of locality names given in labels those have been written in Russian were transliterated according to general directions given by Kerzhner and Nartshuk (1992); localities in labels written in German and English are listed without changes in spelling.

Campiglossa Rondani

Rondani, 1870: 47; 49 (*Oxyina*, subgenus) (type-species: *Tephritis irrorata* Fallén, 1814, by original designation).

Korneyev, 1990: 429 (keys to Eastern Palaearctic species); Merz, 1994: 41 (key to West European species).

Synonyms: *Gonioxyina* Hendel, 1927 (type-species: *Gonioxyina magniceps* Hendel, 1927, by original designation). Synonymized by Korneyev, 1990.

Paroxyina Hendel, 1927 (type-species: *Trypeta tessellata* (sensu Hendel, 1927, nec Loew misidentification of *Trypeta producta* Loew), by original designation; action by ICZN is required to validate designation of *producta* by White, 1986). Synonymized by Merz, 1994.

Smotephritis Chen, 1938 (type-species: *Smotephritis propna* Chen, 1938, by original designation). Synonymized by Korneyev, 1990.

Almiana Hering, 1951 (type-species: *Almiana aliena* Hering, 1951, by original designation). Synonymized by Korneyev, 1990.

Whiterna Korneyev, 1990 (type-species: *Paroxyina loewiana* Hendel, 1927, by original designation). Synonymized by Merz & Freidberg, 1994.

Pseudacmia Korneyev, 1990 (type-species: *Euaesta almiana* Hering, 1937, by original designation). Synonymized by Thompson & al., 1997.

The concept of this genus was revised by Korneyev, 1990, and improved by Merz (1992; 1994). Korneyev (1990) transferred the three species assigned to *Gonioxyina* into *Campiglossa* and keyed them but without further explanations; some species were transferred into *Homoeotricha* Hering by Korneyev (1993; 1995). The present paper aims to supply the previous revisions with the data on the material and redescriptions of the species.

The *magniceps* species group

A key to species

1. The ultimate section of $M(m4) > 2.1$ times longer than the penultimate ($m3$) *C. quadriguttata*
- The ultimate section of $M(m4) < 2.1$ times longer than the penultimate ($m3$) 2.
2. Wing pattern light brown, apical portion of dm with 2–3 partially or completely fused hyaline spots, basal portion of this cell with the spots fused (females not known) *C. magniceps*
- Wing pattern dark brown, apical portion of dm with 4–5 isolated hyaline spots, basal portion of this cell with 4–5 large isolated *C. festiva*

Discussion. The type species of both *Gonioxyina* and *Almiana* fit very near *Campiglossa grandinata* Rondani and *C. misella* Lw. by the structure of the phallus and by the wing pattern. The males of *C. quadriguttata* Hendel, *C. magniceps* Hendel and *C. festiva* Chen resemble males of *Homoeotricha* in having anterior wing margin sharply bowed to bluntly angulate, but clearly differ in the vein R_{2+3} straight, face vertical, not transverse, and by the phallus glans with a long acrophallus (or so-called “rostrum”). Wing patterns of *C. quadriguttata* and *C. festiva* were found to be sexually dimorphic (like in *C. misella* and allied species).

Campiglossa quadriguttata (Hendel)

Hendel, 1927: 158; Foote, 1984: 116 (*Paroxyna*); Korneyev, 1986: 48; 1990: 432; Norrbom in: Thompson et al., 1997 (*Campiglossa*). — *aliena* Hering, 1951: 12; Foote, 1984: 72 (*Almiana*). — *dispertita* Dirlbek, Dirlbek, 1971: 11; Foote, 1984: 74 (*Campiglossa*) (praecoc. Munro, 1957). — *conoepa* Dirlbek, Dirlbekova, 1972: 3; Foote, 1984: 91 (*Gomoxyna*). — *dirlbekorum* Norrbom in: Thompson et al., 1997 (as nom. n. pro *dispertita* Dirlbek, Dirlbek, nec *dispertita* Munro), syn. n.

Type material. Lectotype *Paroxyna quadriguttata* (here designated): ♀. Russia: "Transbaik.<alia>, Pjest-/schanka b. Tschita H. Frieß IX, X '16 [? 78]", "Type ♀" (red paper label); "*Paroxyna quadriguttata* det. Hendel", "Coll. Hendel.", "Type ♀ *Paroxyna quadriguttata* Hendel. Marked by Hardy — 1961" (NHMW) (examined). The second specimen designated by Hendel as the type of *Paroxyna quadriguttata*: ♀. Russia: "Transbaik.<alia>, Picstschanka b. Tschita H. Frieß VI, VII '16 [? 78]", "Type ♀" (red paper label); "*Paroxyna quadriguttata* Type Hendel", "Coll. Hendel.", "Type ♀ *Paroxyna quadriguttata* Hendel. Marked by Hardy — 1961" (NHMW) actually is the female of *Acma biflexa* (examined). Holotypus *Almiana aliena*: ♂. NE China: "Charbin, Mandschurei, 12.VIII.1945, Alin S.// *Almiana aliena* m. gen. n. det M. Hering 1930 <stc!> ♂ Type" (MNHI) (examined). Holotypus *Campiglossa dispertita*: ♀. "Mongolei, Chadchal, 16.VIII.1965 [J. Dlabola, Nr. 27] (NMP) (examined). Holotypus *Gomoxyna conoepa*: ♂. "Mongolei, Ulaanbaatar, 27.VII.1965 [J. Dlabola, Nr. 1] (NMP) (examined). Non-type material. Russia: Irkutsk obl.: vicinity of Chermkhovo, Golumet' vill., 8, 13.08.1928, 2♂, 2 ♀ (*Zonova*) (ZISP); Sarma riv. 200 km NE of Irkutsk, 12.08.1977, ♂ (A. Rasnitsyn) (SIZK); Buryatia: Bain-Gol riv. S of Romanovka, 17–18.07.1961, ♂, ♀ (Pritykina) (ZISP); Amurskaya obl.: Zeya, 19.07.1978, 17.06, 6.08.1981, ♂, 2 ♀ (Shatalkin, Ozerov) (ZMUM); Mongolia: Central Aimak: Songino, 1300 m, 24 km SW v. Ulan-Baator, 13.07.1963, ♀; Ulan-Baator, Nucht im Bogdo ul, 1500–1800 m, 22–23.07, 1600 m, 27.08.1965, 2 ♀ (Exp. Dr. Z. Kaszab) (TMB).

Description. Male. Head (fig. 1–3) yellow, with couple of black, silver tomentose spots on occiput; HR (head ratio)=1.0:1.3:1.6. Frons yellow, matt. Frons as long as wide. Face light yellow, 1.0–1.6 as high as wide (between anterior margins of eyes). Antennae yellow, scape and pedicel black setulose, flagellomere 1 light microtrichose. Arista yellow in basal 1/6, black in the rest. Parafacial matt. Peristomal setulae short and yellow. Eye bare, 1.4–1.5 times higher than long. GHR (gena/eye height ratio) = 0.09–0.14. Proboscis light yellow; labellum rather narrow, never leaf-like broadened; palpi light yellow. Posterior orbital bristles usually black on both sides, but in some specimens white on one on both sides. Occiput white setulose, with 8–10 brown setulae above genal bristles.

Thorax reddish-yellow, grey tomentose, white setulose. Mesonotum with 4 broadly fused stripes of brown tomentum, the two medial reaching prsc ac. Pleura yellow, only anepisternum, katapisternum and katepimerum with black spots. Metanotum black medially, yellow on sides, densely grey tomentose. Scutellum yellow, laterally and basally sometimes darkened.

Wing (fig. 6–7) brown with numerous large hyaline spots; sc completely brown or with a hyaline dot (one ♂ (*Zeya*, 17.07.1981) with a dot on right wing only); r_1 dark field posterior of stigma without lighter dots; 4–6 (usually 5) hyaline spots distally of R_1 ; r_{2+3} basally of r-m with 3–5 dots, distally with 6–8 spots forming 1–2 rows and a couple of isolated or fused spots posteriorly of R_{2+3} apex and another spot at cell apex; br with 7–10 small spots and dots; r_{4+5} with 6–7 dots distally of r-m and 8–10 spots arranged into two rows, isolated or narrowly fused, and with impair apical spot; dm

© V. K. IRINA, 1997

Fig. 1-5 *Campiglossa quadriguttata* (1-3) and *C. magniceps* (4-5) head (голова).
 1, 4 - left view; 2, 5 - anterior view (face, antennae removed), 3 - dorsal view
 (1, 4 - зліва, 2, 5 - спереду, 3 - згори)

with 3–4 large isolate spots basally of r-m and 3–4 small isolate spots; ultimate section of M 2.2–3.5 times longer than the penultimate; the latter hardly as long as dm-cu or shorter. Calypter yellow.

Legs yellow, with dark brown setulae and bristles.

Abdomen yellow with 2 submedial rows of large blackish-brown spots on terga 3–5, white setulose with few black setulae on dark fields.

Male genitalia as on figs 12–15.

Female similar to male, except the costal break much less expressed and the wing hyaline spots smaller (fig. 8).

Wing: sc with a hyaline dot; r_1 dark field posterior of stigma with a small hyaline spot; 3–5 (usually 4) elongate hyaline spots distally of R_1 apex; r_{2+3} basally of r-m with 2 spots, distally with 2–4 spots and 2–3 isolated spots posteriorly of R_{2+3} apex; br with 1–2, rarely 3 small spots; r_{4+5} with 2 spots in basal third and 4–8 spots distally of dm-cu; dm with 2 (rarely 3) large spots basally of r-m and 1–4 (usually 2) small spots at apex.

Tergosternum 7 dark red, basally and apically black, black setulose, as long as 2 last tergites altogether. Aculeus as on figs 16–17; 2 spermathecae (fig. 18)

Body length of male: 4.0–5.3 mm, of female 5.4–6.0 mm.

Wing length of male: 4.4–5.3 mm, of female 5.2–5.7 mm.

Distribution. Russia: Irkutskaya obl., Tshitinskaya obl., Buryatia, Amurskaya obl.; Mongolia; north-eastern China.

Campiglossa magniceps (Hendel)

Hendel, 1927: 161; Chen in: Zia, Chen, 1938: 116; Foote, 1984: 91 (*Paroxyna*); Korneyev, 1990: 433; Norrbom in: Thompson et al., 1997 (*Campiglossa*).

Type material. Lectotype *Gonioxyina magniceps* (designated by inference of holotype by Hardy): ♂. China: “Kuku-nor-Geb./ P. Taucere/ ded. 17.I.1894”, “*Gonioxyina magniceps* det. Hendel”, “Тип ♂” (red paper label “Coll. Hendel.”, “Type ♂ *Gonioxyina magniceps* Hendel. Marked by Hardy — 1961” (NHMW) (examined). **Non-type material.** Central China: “Алашаньские горы, [The Alashan mountains], конейт [end of] VI–VII 1871”, ♂ (Przewalski) (ZISP) (examined); [“W. Kansu: Sing-long-Shan” 10.07.1918, ♂] (IZAS) (not examined).

Description. Resembling *C. quadriguttata*, but differing as follows.

Male. Head (fig. 4–5) HR (head ratio)=1,0:1,4:2,0 in the holotype (head is slightly shrinkled); HR=1.0:1.2:1.5 in the specimen from Alashan. Face as high as wide, slightly deformed in the holotype. Eye bare, 1.7 times higher than long. GHR=0.16–0.20.

Thorax black, except for postpronotal lobe, upper portion of anepisternum and scutellum, grey tomentose, white setulose.

Wing (fig. 9) (see also Hendel, 1927: Taf. XI, Abb. 3) light brown with broadly fused hyaline spots; sc completely brown; r_1 dark field posterior of stigma without lighter dots; 4 (in the holotype) to 5 (the specimen from Alashan) hyaline spots distally of R_1 apex; r_{2+3} basally of r-m with 8–10 dots, distally with 6 spots and another spot at cell apex in the Alashan specimen (wing apex broken up in the holotype); br, r_{4+5} and dm with numerous partially confluent spots; ultimate section of M 1.6–1.8 times longer than the penultimate; the latter longer than dm-cu.

Fig. 6-8. *Campiglossa quadriguttata*, wing (крило).
 6 - male, Golumet'; 7 - male, Charbin (holotype of *A. aliena*); 8 - female, Zeya
 (6 - самець, Голуметь; 7 - самець, Харбін (голотип *A. aliena*); 8 - самця, Зся).

9

10

11

Fig. 9–11. *Campiglossa*, wing (крило).
9 – *C. magniceps*, male, Alashan; 10 – *C. festiva*, male; 11 – *C. festiva* (?), female
(9 – *C. magniceps*, самець, Алашань; 10 – *C. festiva*, самець; 11 – *C. festiva* (?),
самця) (10–11 – after Chen).

Fig. 12-18. *Campiglossa quadriguttata*, genitalia (геніталії)
 12 – epandrium, right view; 13 – left surstylus; 14 – sternum 5; 15 – glans of phallus; 16 – aculeus; 17 – same, enlarged; 18 – spermatheca (12 – епандрій, зправа; 13 – лівий сурстиль; 14 – 5-й стерніт; 15 – гланс фаллюса; 16 – акулеус; 17 – те саме, збільшено; 18 – сперматека) (12-15 – ♂; 16-18 – ♀).

Male genitalia not dissected.

Body length of male: 5.2–5.5 (the holotype)

Wing length of male: 5.5 (the holotype)–5.6 mm.

Distribution. Central China.

Discussion. The lectotype of *G. magniceps* is somewhat teneral, and the Alashan specimen was alcohol-preserved before it was pinned, so they both might be somewhat discolored. This must be kept in mind when comparing it with the following species. Chen (in: Zia, Chen, 1938) mentioned another specimen ["W. Kansu: Sing-long-shan" 10.07.1918, ♂] (IZAS) that I did not examine, but which very probably belongs to this species.

Campiglossa festiva (Chen)

Chen in: Zia, Chen, 1938: 114 (♂); Foote, 1984: 91; Korneyev, 1990: 433 (*Gonioxyna*). — *quadriguttata* Chen in: Zia, Chen, 1938, non Hendel (♀) (misident.) (*Paroxyna*).

Type material. Syntypes *Gonioxyna festiva*: 4 ♂: China: ["Central Shensi <Shaanxi>: Tsinling", 22.08.1916; "S.-E. Shansi <Shanxi>, Choei-mouo-pouo", 28.05.1935] (IZAS) (not examined).

I do not reproduce the original description of *G. festiva* nor redescription of what Chen considered to be *Paroxyna quadriguttata*. Males of *C. festiva* fits near *C. magniceps* differing by darker wing pattern (fig. 10). The females described and figured by Chen as *P. quadriguttata* (China: ["S.-E. Shansi <Shanxi>, Tsin-ou", 21.08.1934, 4 ♀] (IZAS) (not examined) (fig. 11) have the M_3 section much longer than in the specimens from Siberia, Mongolia and North of China, and were certainly misidentified. So far some syntype males of *G. festiva* and those females are originated from south eastern Shanxi, they very probably are conspecific.

Acknowledgements. I thank Dr. Ruth Contreras-Lichtenberg for arranging my visit to Naturhistorisches Museum Wien (NHMW) and for her kind assistance during my work at the collection; the financial support from the Naturhistorisches Museum Wien has been greatly appreciated. Type specimens from NMP were examined through the kindness of Dr. Jan Dirlbek and Dr. Olha Dirlbeková. Thanks are also due to Dr. Bernhard Merz (ETH Zentrum, Zürich) for reading early drafts of the manuscript and critical notes.

References

- Dirlbek J., Dirlbek K. 1971. Ergebnisse der mongolisch-tschechoslowakischen entomologisch-botanischen Expeditionen (1965, 1966) in die Mongolei. Nr. 23: Trypetidae. — *Acta Faun. Entomol. Mus. Natn. Pragae*. 14(156): 9–18.
- Dirlbek J., Dirlbeková O. 1972. Neue Bohrfliegenarten (Diptera, Trypetidae) aus der Mongolei — *Annot. zool.-bot. Bratisl.* 77(7): 1–5.
- Foote R. H. 1984. Family Tephritidae (Trypetidae). In: Soós Á., Papp L., eds. *Catalogue of Palaearctic Diptera*. Vol. 9. *Micropezidae — Agromyzidae*. — Budapest, Akadémiai Kiadó: 66–149.
- Hendel F. 1927. 49. Trypetidae. In: Lindner E., Ed. *Die Fliegen der paläarktischen Region*. Stuttgart, E. Schweizerbart. Verl. (Erwin Nägele): 5(Lfg. 16–19): 221 S.
- Hering E. M. 1951. Neue Fruchtfliegen der Alten Welt. — *Siruna Seva*. (7): 1–16.

- Kerzhner I. M., Nartshuk E. P. 1992. Recommendations for spelling Russian names and titles. — *Folia Entomol. Hung. — Rovart. Kozl.* 53: 71–88.
- Korneyev V. A. [1990]. A review of *Sphenella* and *Paroxyna* series of genera (Diptera, Tephritidae, Tephritinae) of Eastern Palaearctic. — *Nasekomye Mongolii*. Leningrad, Nauka: 1989, 11: 395–470. (In Russian; English summary¹)
- Merz B. 1992. *Revision der westpalaearktischen Gattungen und Arten der Paroxyna-Gruppe und Revision der Fruchtfliegen der Schweiz (Diptera, Tephritidae)*. [Zürich]: 341 S. (Dissertation ETH Nr. 9902)
- Merz B. 1994. *Diptera Tephritidae*. Genève: 198 S. (Insecta Helvetica. Fauna. — 10.)
- Merz B., Freidberg A. 1994. Nomenclatural changes in the Tephritidae (Diptera). — *Israel J. Entomol.* 28: 171–172.
- Rondani C. 1870. *Diptera Italicae prodromus. Genera Italica ordinis dipterorum ordinatim disposita et distincta et in familias et stripes aggregata. 7 (pars 4) (sect. 1). Parmae*: 59 p.
- Thompson F. C., Norrbom A. L., Carroll L. E., Freidberg A., White I. M. 1997. *Fruit Fly BioSystematic Information Database and Expert System*. — Washington.
- White I. M. 1986. A new species of *Paroxyna* Hendel and notes on the nomenclature of other British Tephritidae (Diptera). — *Entomol. Mon. Mag.* 122: 145–163.
- Zia Y., Chen S. H. 1938. Trypetidae of North China. — *Sinensia.* 9(1–2): 180 p.